

Paper 6**ASSESSING THE INFLUENCE OF SOFT SKILL TRAINING ON STUDENTS' EMPLOYABILITY – A STUDENT'S PERSPECTIVE****Shwetha.T. S¹, & Nethravathi P. S²**¹Research Scholar, College of Management and Commerce,
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ORCIDID:0000-0001-5447-8673; Email: nethrakumar590@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

The education system today is changing drastically and there is a dire need to infuse students with both hard and soft skills that the corporate world expects. Employers do not look for individuals with only excellent academic records and experience. To excel in the Corporate World one needs to be self-directed, ethical and most importantly resourceful with good interpersonal skills. Dearth in the candidates meeting these requirements is causing decrease in the placement drives at institutional levels. This paper aims at understanding the influence of soft skills training on the employability of students and thereby emphasizing the importance of incorporating soft skill training as part of the curriculum at the institutional level. The study takes into account the responses of students from various institutions with and without exposure to soft skill training programme in order to assess the influence of soft skills training on their employability.

Keywords: Soft Skill, Training, Personality Development, Employability**1. INTRODUCTION**

The education system is going through a drastic change and so is the recruitment and selection procedures of corporates. It is becoming increasingly difficult for fresh graduates to have a successful career regardless of their academic performance. Corporates now prefer individuals who add value to the organization with their special skill sets apart from academic excellence. Soft skills such as communication skills, team work, self - motivation, leadership skills, interpersonal skills and critical thinking ability are increasingly becoming the most sought-after quality of an individual by most corporate recruiters. Therefore, in today's corporate environment for individuals to succeed in their career they need to have a competitive edge which distinguishes them from individuals with similar qualifications. Thus, having a formal soft-skill training at the institutional level along with their professional curriculum will help them develop their personality and help them secure a successful position in the corporate arena.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURES ON SOFT-SKILLS TRAINING

Soft skills are essentially the attributes or specific skills that enable individuals to network well with others. According to John, J. (2009) "soft skills are non-technical, intangible, personality specific skills which determines an individual's strength as a leader, listener and negotiator or as a conflict mediator". In the words of Tobin (2006), "Soft skills are the traits and abilities of

attitude and behaviour rather than of knowledge or technical aptitude”. The significance of soft skill training or personality development programs have been recognized globally and many institutions are aware of the benefits of having an association with the finishing schools for training their students in soft skills. The training programs guarantee the expected outcomes with regard to the soft skill one needs to possess with a viable assessment to measure the impact. Unlike hard skills such as academic performance softs skills are hard to measure and the outcome cannot be assessed easily. In the study conducted by Thacker and Yost (2002) stressed on the importance of soft-skills in B-schools in order to be a team player as employers felt that graduates lack team leadership skills. Additionally, Knell and et.al. (2007) conducted a study, which revealed that HR managers prefer candidates with creative thinking, good communication and cultural understanding. On the other hand, poor communication skill has an adverse impact on selection process during recruitment as rightly cited by Pauw et al (2006).

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main aim of the study is to understand the influence of softs skills training on the employability of students. The secondary objectives are;

- To understand the major soft skill parameters that can be significantly improved by providing soft skill training.
- To understand the importance of incorporating soft skill training as part of the curriculum at the institutional level.

4. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted post-test experimental research design taking into account responses from students of Management Institutes in and around Dakshina Kannada district. The students were grouped into two categories one with soft skill training and the other without the soft skill training. The total sample size of 80 students were selected based on simple random sampling technique. Out of which 40 students are with soft skill training (Experimental group) and other 40 without soft skill training (Control group). The study compared the responses of both the groups for 20 parameters relating to soft skills with the help of Likert’s scale. The deviations between the groups were used to measure the impact of soft skill on the control group. The responses were analyzed using SPSS software.

5. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The first objective is to understand the impact of soft skill training. To achieve this objective T-Test is performed on both the groups to understand if there is any significant difference between the mean scores of two groups. The results of the T-test are shown in the table below. The result of the T-Test shows that the experimental group that is the group with soft skill training has significantly higher soft skills as compared to the other group with the test-statistics of 16.73 which is highly significant at 0.01 level of confidence. This implies that soft skill training plays a significant role in students’ employability skills. The secondary objective of the study is to identify the important soft skill parameters that can be improved with a proper soft skill training. The table below shows the comparison between the mean values of experimental and control group to identify the significantly different Soft Skill Parameters. The Analysis of

the study show case that, most of the parameters of soft skills significantly differ between two groups.

	Mean	SD	N	T-Test	P-Value
With Soft Skill Training	87.60	14.85	40	16.73**	0.00
Without Soft Skill Training	38.20	11.31	40		
** : significant at 0.01 level					

The parameters like Communication, Ethics and Stress Management have a higher mean value for experimental group with soft skill training as compared to the control group without soft skill training, which is significant at 99% confidence level. There is also statistical evidence claiming that the parameters such as Team Work, Critical Thinking, Adaptability, Leadership, Technical Skills, Academic Skills, Time Management, Influencing Skills and Written Communication have a higher mean value in Experimental Group, which is statistically significant at 95% confidence level and Creativity is significantly higher at 90% confidence level.

6. CONCLUSION

Today, corporates prefer candidates who are self- motivated, value driven with both soft and specialized hard skills to work in their organization. The individual should have good interpersonal skills along with better communication in order to be a team player. Creativity, Critical Thinking and stress management skills are the need of the hour in today's corporate environment. Thus, educational institutes should not only focus on bringing out academically strong graduates but also graduates who are job ready with all the soft skills that the industry requires. This can be achieved only by having a detailed and structured soft skill training program at the institutional level, which is very much evident from the findings of the study. Thus, educational institutes should focus on having soft skills training as part of the curriculum for management students, which will make them more compatible with the corporate environment.

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